

ON THE MODE OF REACTIVITY OF ORCINOL WITH MALIC ACID.

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By condensing orcinol with ethyl acetoacetate Pechmann and Cohen (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2188) obtained a substance to which they assigned the formula, 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin, from analogy with the condensation of resorcinol with the same ester. The constitution of this compound was later investigated by Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1614) who established it as 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin from a detailed investigation of the corresponding coumarin-4-acetic acid.

Pechmann and Welsh (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1649) condensed orcinol with malic acid in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid and described the product as 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin. As a result of the above-mentioned work of Dey there has been a tendency to regard this compound also as a 5-hydroxycoumarin derivative (Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 793). But the coumarin obtained by them exhibits marked fluorescence when dissolved in aqueous alkali or in concentrated sulphuric acid and in this respect behaves differently from 5-hydroxycoumarins. Ranganadhras (M.Sc. thesis, Andhra University, 1940) has, however, recorded the formation of some quantity of 5-hydroxy-7-methylcoumarin besides the 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin and the coumarino- α -pyrone, by using a higher molecular proportion of malic acid and heating at 100° (*cf* Sen and Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*). It appears, therefore, that orcinol behaves in two different ways in respect of its nuclear reactivity with malic acid. The simultaneous reactivity of both the β and γ positions of orcinol has been observed by Desai and Vakil (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 12A, 391) in the case of the internal Friedel and Crafts' reaction. The synthesis of 5-hydroxy-7-methylcoumarin starting from ethyl haematommate has been described by Sastry and Seshadri (*ibid.*, 1940, 12A, 498) and this compound is very different from the isomer obtained by Pechmann and Welsh and its solutions are deep yellow in colour without fluorescence. Consequently their compound should be 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin whose synthesis starting from orcylic aldehyde has been described by Rao and Seshadri (*ibid.*, 1941, 13A, 253). The author has studied these condensations in greater detail by employing varying molecular proportions of malic acid and heating at different temperatures.

Orcinol and malic acid in equimolecular proportions, were condensed according to the method of Pechmann and Welsh (*loc. cit.*). After adding

sulphuric acid the mixture was heated over a wire gauze using a micro-burner until the reaction was complete.

The product was obtained as pale yellow flat needles and tablets, m.p. 248° . It gave no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. Its solution in aqueous alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid was colourless exhibiting blue fluorescence. It was found to be identical with 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin (Rao and Seshadri, *loc. cit.*).

The above experiment was repeated using a water-bath kept at $70-80^{\circ}$ for heating the mixture. After heating for 3 hours the product was worked up and found to be 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin. Similar results were obtained on repeating the experiment with two molecular proportions of malic acid.

By condensing orcinol (1 mol.) and malic acid (1.5 mol) on the water-bath (3 hours) in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid a yellow product was obtained which left on boiling with an insufficient amount of alcohol, a fairly good quantity of white residue. This residue (A) was exhausted with alcohol to remove the yellow substance (B) associated with it and then recrystallised from pyridine or glacial acetic acid when colourless needles melting at 345° were obtained. This substance is sparingly soluble in ether, chloroform and benzene and moderately soluble in boiling alcohol and acetone. It is insoluble in ammonia, but dissolves in hot caustic alkalis with a yellow colour and is identified as a coumarino- α -pyrone.

The yellow alcoholic solution obtained above was concentrated to a small volume when the substance (B) crystallised out. On further crystallisation pale yellow flat needles and tablets of 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin, melting at 248° , were obtained. The substance does not give a colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride. It dissolves in aqueous alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid with blue fluorescence. The same products were obtained even when 2 mols. of malic acid were employed.

These experiments were repeated by heating orcinol at 120° with different proportion (1, 1.5, and 2 mols.) of malic acid and the results were similar to those obtained above excepting that some resinification took place probably due to the high temperature employed.

From these experiments it is, therefore, to be concluded that orcinol reacts with malic acid only in the β -position and consequently no 5-hydroxy-7-methylcoumarin is produced.